

THE IMPACT OF ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE ON HUMAN RESOURCES SATISFACTION (MODEL OF "SPORTS FEDERATIONS IN THE KINGDOM OF BAHRAIN")

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Abstract

The study entitled "The Impact of Organizational Justice on Human Resources Satisfaction (Model of "Sports Federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain")" explores the extent of the impact of organizational justice by knowing the nature of the relationship between the study variables and their extent of association with sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain as a model. To reach the goal of the study, the researcher decided to follow the descriptive analytical approach by using a questionnaire that includes the study variables (organizational justice and job satisfaction of human resources) for the study community consisting of (1500) human resources working in the sports federations of the Kingdom of Bahrain. The study sample was selected from the study community, which consists of (288) human resources, or (20%) of the original community size, where Likert scale of five levels was used to answer the questionnaire. The researcher reached a set of results, which consisted of 10 results, the most important of which is (the satisfaction of human resources in sports federations is affected by the level of organizational justice practiced in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain in general and distributive justice in particular), the study also recommended the need of the incentive distribution system to a continuous develop that aims to focus on the efforts of human resources in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain directly and tangibly, and therefore incentives must be linked to the performance of human resources, in addition to other recommendations.

Keywords: Organizational Justice, Human Resources, Sports Federations.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are considered one of the most important resources in the sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain, as they have a major role in the production process in all their activities. They are responsible for planning, implementation, organization, control, decision-making, and following up on workflow procedures in order to achieve the vision, mission, and goals of these federations.

The behavior of human resources is of great interest to officials and scholars, in order to discover the factors that contribute to and affect it and how to deal with them. In general, organizational strategic policies and work procedures are the main factor that affects the behavior of human resources, including organizational justice, which contributes significantly to explaining the behavior of human resources and their level of job satisfaction towards the sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain.

Organizational justice is the focus of many researchers in the field of administrative studies, especially those concerned with organizational behavior, due to its great importance and direct

relationship to a set of organizational variables (the job performance of human resources) that have a significant impact on the success of sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain and the extent to which they achieve their goals.

Job performance occupies a prominent position in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain, due to its association with the human resources working there, which is considered the most important resource thereof, as they are primarily responsible for improving their performance. The human resources achievement of outstanding job performance is dependent on the availability of a sufficient level of organizational justice, whether at the material or human level. Excellent job performance is not achieved without the existence of organizational justice, which is represented in (fairness, equality) among all human resources working in there. This has a positive impact on the behavior of human resources, their response and understanding of situations, in addition to creating a positive climate and linking the goals of both human resources and sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain.

Organizational justice and job performance of human resources are closely related, as it is not possible to achieve outstanding performance without the existence of organizational justice that enhances the sense of belonging, satisfaction, and pride in sports federations. Therefore, the study investigates the impact of organizational justice on human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain.

Study Problem

Organizational justice is a critical requirement for its positive impact on the performance of human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain. This led the researcher, from an administrative and organizational perspective, to investigate it, especially in the field of sports. The human resource in sports federations performs various tasks inside and outside the organization, which creates a feeling of pressure in the work environment and makes it ready for decreasing its level of job satisfaction if sports federations do not achieve organizational justice.

Despite the emphasis on the importance of recognizing organizational justice in the sports work environment as the main determinant of human resources satisfaction, the current reality of the work environment in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain indicates the existence of some shortcomings that may weaken the perceptions of organizational justice among human resources, which reduces their level of job satisfaction, which consequently causes a deficiency in the overall performance in a sports institution that is an interface for the Kingdom of Bahrain. The study problem is highlighted in the following main question:

Is there a statistically significant effect at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) of organizational justice on the satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain?

The main question gives rise to the following sub-questions:

1. Is there a statistically significant effect at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) of the reality of organizational justice in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain?
2. Is there a statistically significant effect at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) of the reality of job satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain due to demographic variables (gender, age, years of experience, type of work)?
3. Is there a statistically significant effect at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) of organizational justice on job satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain due to demographic variables (gender, age, years of experience, type of work)?

Study Hypotheses

H1: There is a statistically significant effect at the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) in the opinions of the sample on the impact between the organizational justice of human resources in sports federations attributed to demographic variables (gender, age, years of experience, type of work).

Study Significance

1. Theoretical significance: It lies in the fact that it is one of the first and minority studies and research that studies one of the important administrative concepts such as organizational justice in its relationship with the job satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain.
2. Practical significance: The practical importance of the research lies in the results and recommendations that the study reaches, which can be benefited from by the administrative leaderships in sports federations in particular and public institutions in general in the Kingdom of Bahrain.

Study Objectives

1. To know the reality of the prevailing organizational justice in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain in terms of type and level.
2. To know the reality of the job satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain according to demographic variables (gender, age, years of experience, type of work).
3. To explain the role of prevailing organizational justice on the job satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain.
4. To formulate and present some recommendations and proposals that seek to increase the job satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain.

Terms of the Study

Organizational justice is the perception of human resources that there is fairness and equality between what it provides to the institution and what it produces from outputs, so that there is a balance between inputs and outputs that arise from the prevailing relationship in the institution, which includes the relationships of human resources with managers, colleagues of the same work rank, and with the institution as a social system (Ramadaniya, 2022, p. 8).

Distribution justice is the justice of the outputs that the human resource receives, that is, it is the justice concerned with the distribution of rewards, and it is related to the results or outputs that the human resource obtains from his job, especially the outputs of distributing wages and promotions, which achieves the perception of human resources after the distribution of justice in the institution in the event of the human resource feeling that what he gets from rewards is commensurate with his effort compared to his colleagues (Kharmous, 2014, p.: 49).

Procedural justice is the perception of the human resource for the fairness of organizational procedures for making decisions concerning the distribution of return, such as performance evaluation procedures, which are achieved by allowing him to discuss the procedures and participate in making them (Ramadaniya, 2022, p. 9).

Transactional justice is the degree of human resources' sense of good treatment between colleagues at work, and this is done by treating them with attention, respect, and the presence of justice and trust between them (Mahamdi, Sharif, 2022, p. 9).

Job performance is the practices and behaviors that human resources show towards the implementation of tasks and responsibilities, and the outputs resulting from them, and the extent of their quality and compliance with the specifications required for job performance (Al-Wakeel, 2021, p. 116).

Job satisfaction is the feeling of human resources of general satisfaction with their job, synchronized with the psychological feeling of complete acceptance of what they get from outputs (incentives and benefits) due to what they provide from inputs to the institution to which they belong, which achieves happiness and psychological comfort, through the interaction with the capabilities that affect the performance behavior that human resources show in the work environment from motivation, enthusiasm, and desire to carry out the tasks assigned to them according to the intensity of the effort he exerts and the degree of his perseverance and continuity and providing the best of his abilities and skills (Tumbouz, 2022, p. 127).

Application of Organizational Justice in Sports Federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain

The Bahrain Olympic Committee was founded in 1979 and registered under Law No. (21) Of 1989 issued on June 26, 1990, under No. (3) Regarding the regulation of clubs and associations in the field of youth and sports in the General Authority for Youth and Sports and has a legal personality from the date of its publication in the Official Gazette. The idea of establishing a committee was on May 19, 1979, where it became the official institution supervising sports activities in Bahrain and affiliated to the Supreme Council for Youth and Sports, which was

founded in 1975, headed by Crown Prince Hamad bin Isa Al Khalifa, following the founding meeting on May 19, 1979, in the presence of representatives of nine sports federations, which are athletics, swimming, football, basketball, volleyball, handball, weightlifting, table tennis, and shooting. The committee's bylaws were adopted and submitted to the Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs, which was supervising the national clubs and sports federations. The vision of the Bahrain Olympic Committee is "to empower human resources working in the Olympic movement to achieve sustainable excellence." Its mission is to "protect, develop and organize the sports movement in the Kingdom of Bahrain in accordance with the Olympic Charter by strengthening partnerships with relevant parties."

The importance of organizational justice is highlighted following what was mentioned in the vision of the Bahrain Olympic Committee, as it considers organizational justice to be one of the most important components of the social and psychological structure of the committee. It represents the value and social pattern, and any attack on it by the institution represents the destruction of the values and social relations of human resources. Therefore, the lack of justice leads to human resources following harmful behaviors to the institution. (Goldman, 2004)

Internal justice occurs at the Bahrain Olympic Committee when the material return that the human resource working there receives is equal to the relative value of the job within the institution. External justice is achieved when the material return that the human resource working there receives is equal to that which the workers who perform similar work in other institutions receive. (Omyan, 2005, P. 289) The success of the Bahrain Olympic Committee can be judged by the ability of its senior management to achieve the requirements of organizational justice, and the extent of its ability to urge the human resources working there to demonstrate the desired behaviors, and what embodies their organizational commitment and organizational citizenship towards their organizations to which they belong. (al fahdawi, al qatawneh, 2004, p. 3)

The Concept of Organizational Justice

The concept of organizational justice dates back to the equity theory proposed by Adams (1963), which states that "employees tend to judge justice by comparing their inputs to the outcomes they receive and then comparing that to their colleagues. If employees perceive injustice according to the results of the previous comparison, this may lead to a state of tension for the employee, which may result in some deviant behaviors such as absenteeism and neglect, etc." (Al-Buainin, 2016, p. 49). It is a "perception of employees that they receive returns commensurate with the effort they exert, their involvement in making decisions related to their job, and their sense of being treated objectively and respectfully within the organization" (Mahamadi and Sharif, 2022, p. 9)

The Structural Framework of Organizational Justice

A number of researchers have developed frameworks for the components of organizational justice. One of the most prominent frameworks was developed by Leventhal (1980), who identified six basic rules that together constitute the structural framework of organizational justice.

These rules are as follows (Al-Fadl and Al-Anezi, 2007, p. 48):

1. The presence of real opportunities for review and modification of decisions.
2. The distribution of resources on ethical bases and standards.
3. The consideration of the views and perspectives of those involved in the decision-making process.
4. Impartiality and avoidance of personal interests in decision-making.
5. Making decisions based on accurate and sound information.
6. The fairness of applying the reward and punishment procedures to all individuals, under different circumstances and times.

The Importance of Organizational Justice

The importance of organizational justice can be summarized as follows (Fahdawi and Qatawneh, 2004, pp. 15-16):

1. It clarifies the true nature of the distribution system for wages and salaries in the organization, through distributive justice.
2. It leads to the achievement of actual control and empowerment in the decision-making process, through procedural justice.
3. Organizational justice is reflected behaviorally in the states of satisfaction with supervisors and decision-making systems, and on citizenship behaviors and organizational commitment.
4. It shines a light on revealing the organizational atmosphere and the prevailing climate in the organization, which is what is highlighted by interpersonal justice.
5. Determining the quality of the monitoring, control, and evaluation system, and the ability to activate feedback roles, in a way that guarantees the sustainability of organizational processes and achievements for members of the organization.
6. It highlights the social, ethical, and religious values of individuals, and determines the ways of interaction and moral maturity among members of the organization in how they perceive and conceive of the common justice in the organization.

Dimensions of Organizational Justice

Organizational justice is one of the most important concepts in organizational psychology, which deals with the degree to which employees feel fair in their dealings with the organization. Organizational justice is divided into three main dimensions, namely:

- **Distributional Justice:** It is the first component of organizational justice, which was studied by specialists in social psychology (Al-Hameedi, 2012, p. 63). It focuses on two elements: the opinion of human resources on the fairness of what they receive from sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain compared to what they believe they offer them,

and the opinion of human resources on the fairness of what they receive from those sports federations compared to other human resources working in similar conditions to them, whether in the same institution or outside, and it is represented in three rules: the rule of equality, the rule of quality, and the rule of need (Yilmaz&Tasdan, 2009: P113).

- Procedural justice: is "the degree of feeling generated among human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain regarding the fairness of organizational procedures used to determine organizational outcomes" (Al-Fahdawi and Qatouna, 2004, p. 10), and it consists of 6 rules: the rule of appeal, the rule of ethics, the rule of representation, the rule of non-bias, the rule of accuracy, and the rule of consistency. It also consists of several components, which are: the stability of procedures, the validity of procedures, the reality of procedures and their ethics, and non-bias (Mahram, 2000, p. 326). It is a combination of regular justice and informational justice (Al-Hameedi, 2012, p. 67).
- Fairness of treatment it is the degree to which human resources (HR) professionals working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain feel that they are treated fairly (humanly and organizationally) when implementing procedures. It consists of four basic dimensions: "honesty, respect, courtesy, and trust between management and HR" (Husted & Folger, 2004). It includes two types of fairness: "relational justice, which refers to the level of respect and appreciation with which the manager deals with the subordinates, and information justice, which focuses on the explanations provided to HR professionals through the delivery of the necessary information about the reasons for using certain procedures or the way of allocating certain outputs in a reliable and certain manner" (Rego & Cunha, 2006:7). It includes several elements: "the manager's treatment of his subordinates with respect and appreciation, the manager's treatment of his subordinates fairly without bias, providing important information to justify the actions taken upon request, the accuracy and realism of the information provided to subordinates, and providing it on time" (Bagoodah, 2009, p. 40).
- Job satisfaction is defined as "a positive emotional state resulting from the evaluation of the work or job experience." It arises in human resources as a result of the human resource's perception of the extent to which their jobs provide those things that they see as important. In the field of organizational behavior, it is generally accepted that job satisfaction is the most important attitude (VICTORIA, 2015). It is also a "sum of the elements of satisfaction that the human resource imagines that they will get from their work, in a more specific form (Zozo, 2016, p. 50), which instills a psychological feeling of satisfaction, comfort, and happiness to satisfy the needs, desires, and expectations with the work environment, the work itself, and with trust, loyalty, and belonging to it" (Lekheli, 2018, p. 55).

The Directions that Explain the Satisfaction of Human Resources

There are many directions that have tried to explain job satisfaction. There is the direction of human relations, which assumes that job satisfaction is the main driver of motivation. There is the approach based on the results of behavioral theories, which assumes that motivation is affected by previous experiences of reward and punishment. There is a third approach that is the product of studies in cognitive psychology, which assumes that motivation is the product of the interaction of variables and psychological processes that are latent within the individual.

The human direction sees that the individual's feeling of happiness and satisfaction of his needs at work lead to a sense of job satisfaction. Maslow (Maslow) clarified human needs and their hierarchy of satisfaction, and affirmed that human resources, if they feel that these needs are satisfied in their job, feel satisfied with it.

The behavioral direction confirms that job satisfaction is affected by previous experiences of reward and punishment in their responses to work requirements. Therefore, the higher the level of reward, whether material or moral, the higher the level of job satisfaction. The lower the level of reward, the lower the level of job satisfaction.

The cognitive direction emphasizes the importance of the individual's perception of the factors affecting work. The more positive these perceptions are, the more they contribute to job satisfaction. If they are negative, they lead to a decrease in job satisfaction. (Muhammad, 2015)

Job Satisfaction Factors

There are many factors that affect job satisfaction, which are divided into two main categories: personal factors and professional factors. Personal factors include physical and health characteristics, abilities and predispositions, emotional or affective traits of the individual, and the desire to work. Any profession requires the individual to have special qualities that qualify him to perform its requirements. Professional factors, on the other hand, include the working conditions and nature of the work in terms of the effort that the individual exerts in it, the number of hours, vacations, and the nature of the work if it is vital or training. It also includes opportunities for promotion and progress in work, the status of the profession, and the relationship with superiors and colleagues. Professional satisfaction is a "result of several variables, and it is calculated through all that is expected from work and what is obtained by the individual" (Yılmaz, 2013).

Previous Studies

Arabic Studies

Study of Tanbouz, Bashar (2022), entitled "**The level of organizational justice and its relationship to the level of job performance of employees in Palestinian universities from the perspective of faculty members (a case study of the Palestinian Technical University - Kadoorie)**".

The study aimed to identify the level of organizational justice in Palestinian universities from the perspective of faculty members, in addition to identifying the level of job performance of

human resources working in them from the perspective of faculty members, and to identify the role of the variables (gender and academic rank) in the difference in the responses of faculty members towards the level of organizational justice and the level of job performance of human resources in Palestinian universities. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach and the questionnaire were used as a tool for the study. The study population consisted of (268) faculty members, and the study sample consisted of (159) members. The results of the study showed that the level of organizational justice in Palestinian universities from the perspective of faculty members came in a large degree, and the results did not show any statistically significant differences attributed to the variable (gender and academic rank) towards the level of organizational justice and the level of job performance of human resources in Palestinian universities. It also showed a positive relationship between both organizational justice and job performance. The study recommended working to apply the standards of organizational justice for its positive indicators on job performance, and the trend to increase material incentives that increase the level of job performance and the competitive advantage of universities.

Study of Ibrahim, Samer, Abdel Nasser, Rasha (2022), entitled "Organizational justice as a variable to address occupational burnout of employees in higher education institutions".

The study aimed to identify occupational burnout, measure the dimensions and indicators of occupational burnout of human resources working in higher education institutions, in addition to measuring the dimensions of organizational justice and its relationship to alleviating the severity of occupational burnout of human resources working in higher education institutions, and to investigate the possibility of applying organizational justice to address this occupational burnout through indicators. The study concluded with the acceptance of all hypotheses, and a future vision to overcome the difficulties and obstacles that limit occupational burnout of human resources working in higher education institutions.

Foreign Studies

Study of Khawaja jehanzed, 2020, entitled "The mediating role of organizational commitment between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior: Power distance as moderator".

The study aimed to investigate the relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), the mediating effect of organizational commitment, and the moderating role of power distance in this association. The study used stratified sampling technique, and data were collected from human resources working in bank branches located in five urban cities (i.e., Islamabad, Peshawar, Lahore, Quetta, and Karachi) in Pakistan. A total of 409 responses were received and 379 questionnaires were considered for analysis. To test the hypotheses, structural equation modeling technique was applied using AMOS210 program. The results of the study showed that there was a non-significant relationship between organizational justice and organizational commitment, and that organizational commitment fully mediates the relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship

behavior. Power distance moderates the relationship between organizational justice and organizational commitment.

Study of Rami M. Ayoubi and Hiba Massoud, 2019, entitled "Transformational leadership, organizational justice and organizational outcomes: A study from the higher education sector in Syria"

The study aimed to investigate the impact of transformational leadership on the mediating role of organizational justice on organizational commitment in Syria in the higher education sector. Data were collected from 502 human resources working in six higher education institutions. Two measures of organizational outcomes were selected for this study, using the OC and JS equation model, namely job satisfaction and organizational structure. The results of the study showed that there was a statistically significant relationship between transformational leadership in the mediating role of organizational justice on organizational commitment.

The study of H. Muhammad Arifin (2015), entitled "The Influence of Competence, Motivation, and Organizational Culture to High School Teacher Job Satisfaction and Performance"

The study aimed to investigate the impact of competence, motivation, and organizational culture in the secondary school environment on both job satisfaction and job performance of teachers in Jayapura City, Papua, Indonesia. The study was conducted on 117 teachers out of 346 teachers, and the data was analyzed using SEM analysis. The results indicate that competence and organizational culture have a positive and statistically significant impact on job satisfaction and job performance of high school teachers, while motivation has a more positive impact on job performance of teachers. In fact, organizational culture had no impact on job satisfaction.

Data Collection Methods

The study adopted the descriptive-analytical approach as the appropriate approach for the study's variables, objectives, and hypotheses, to determine the impact of organizational justice prevailing in the sports federations of the Kingdom of Bahrain on the job satisfaction of human resources working there. This approach aims to describe the characteristics of the study problem in a precise and comprehensive manner, and to identify the current reality and measure it through a questionnaire prepared for this purpose, as well as to identify the relationships that exist between the variables, relying on collecting facts and analyzing them to extract the results, and making recommendations and proposals that would serve other researchers. The researcher relied on collecting the information concerned with the study from primary sources "data from the study sample members through the questionnaire prepared by the researcher", and secondary sources "Arabic and foreign books, journals, doctoral and master's theses, in addition to electronic sites with a sports and scientific nature".

The study population consists of all human resources working in the sports federations of the Kingdom of Bahrain, where the number of human resources working there is (1500) human resources in the technical and administrative fields in its various departments, which number

(24). A representative sample of the study population was selected through the random sampling method, with a sample size of (288) human resources working in the various sports federations. (300) questionnaires were distributed to the study sample at a rate of (20%) of the original research community, and (291) were retrieved. After reviewing them, it was found that there were (3) incomplete questionnaires, so they were excluded.

The Study Variables are:

- The independent variable: organizational justice, which branches out from this variable into three dimensions: (distributive justice, interactional justice, procedural justice) according to the model of (Kursad Yilmaz, Yahya Altinkurt Gizem Karaman, 2015).
- The dependent variable: job satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain, which branches out into the following dimensions according to the model of Cevat ELMA (2013): (satisfaction with wages and bonuses, satisfaction with promotions, satisfaction with supervision).

Verification of the Study Hypotheses

Results of the Verification of the First Hypothesis

H1: There is a statistically significant impact between organizational justice and the satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain.

The main hypothesis gives rise to the following sub-hypotheses:

- A. There is a statistically significant impact between distributive justice and job satisfaction.
- B. There is a statistically significant impact between procedural justice and job satisfaction.
- C. There is a statistically significant impact between interactional justice and job satisfaction.

To verify the validity of this hypothesis, the researcher verified the level of the correlational relationship by calculating the correlation coefficients between the three dimensions of organizational justice (distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice) according to the opinions of human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain, using Pearson's equation through the SPSS program, and the following results were found:

According to the correlation matrix, it is clear that all dimensions of organizational justice are associated with the dimensions of job satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations with a statistically significant relationship at the significance level (0.01), and that organizational justice in general is associated with a strong relationship with the job satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations.

To verify the extent of the impact of organizational justice on the job satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations, multiple regression analysis was conducted, and the following results were obtained:

The statistical data in the table of multiple linear regression analysis indicate that there is a statistically significant effect at the significance level of (0.01) for the three dimensions of organizational justice (distribution, procedures, and interaction) on the job satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations. This is evidenced by the high value of the calculated F, and that it was statistically significant, as the probability value reached (0.00), which is less than the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), and this is reinforced by the value of the correlation coefficient, which reached 0.762.

It can also be said that the three dimensions of organizational justice explain 54.5% of the job satisfaction of human resources, based on the value of the determination coefficient ($R^2 = 0.545$). Based on this; the first hypothesis is accepted.

The impact of each dimension of the three dimensions of organizational justice on the job satisfaction of human resources was revealed, and the following was found:

The most explanatory and influential dimension of organizational justice on job satisfaction is distributive justice, followed by procedural justice, and finally interactional justice. From here, it can be said that the first hypothesis of the research has been achieved and its validity has been proven, and based on this we accept all the sub-hypotheses that emanate from this hypothesis as follows:

- A. There is a statistically significant effect between distributive justice and job satisfaction.
- B. There is a statistically significant effect between procedural justice and job satisfaction.
- C. There is a statistically significant effect between interactional justice and job satisfaction.

Results of the Verification of the Second Hypothesis

The Hypothesis States

There are statistically significant differences in the sample's views on the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations, due to the following demographic variables: gender, age, educational qualification, years of experience, and type of work.

1. Verification of the differences between the sample members by gender

To verify the validity of this hypothesis, Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated to determine the size and type of the correlational relationship between the independent variable (organizational justice) and the dependent variable (job satisfaction) for both male and female human resources. The following was found:

There are differences in the views of male and female human resources on the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction. Here we see that female human resources working in sports federations believe that their job satisfaction depends heavily on the level of

organizational justice practiced in the federation, more than male human resources who believe that their job satisfaction also depends on the level of organizational justice, but to a lesser extent than females.

Therefore, it can be said that the results were consistent with what the second hypothesis stated regarding the differences between human resources on the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction, which is due to gender.

2. Verification of the differences between the sample members by age

To verify the validity of this variable, Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated to determine the size and type of the correlational relationship between the independent variable (organizational justice) and the dependent variable (job satisfaction) for human resources working in sports federations based on the following ages: (less than 25 years), (26-34), (35-44), and (45 or more).

The following was found:

Human resources working in sports federations who are between the ages of (26-34) are the most human resources in their views that the correlational relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction is a strong relationship, which means that this age group of human resources their job satisfaction increases significantly as they perceive that there is a real application of organizational justice in the federation compared to other age groups. This is followed by human resources who are between the ages of (35-44), then human resources who are less than 25 years old, and the last place is held by human resources whose ages are over 45 years, which means that older human resources do not see that there is a significant relationship between their job satisfaction and the level of organizational justice applied in the federation. Therefore, it can be said that the results were consistent with what the second hypothesis stated regarding the differences between human resources on the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction, which is due to age.

3. Verification of the differences between sample members by educational qualification

To verify the validity of this variable, Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated to determine the size and type of the correlational relationship between the independent variable (organizational justice) and the dependent variable (job satisfaction) for human resources working in sports federations based on the following educational qualifications: (less than Bachelor's degree, Bachelor's degree, and graduate studies). The following was found:

Human resources working in sports federations with a Bachelor's degree are the most human resources in their views that the correlational relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction is a strong relationship.

This means that these human resources experience a significant increase in job satisfaction as they perceive that there is a real application of organizational justice in the federation compared to other educational qualifications. This is followed by human resources with less than a Bachelor's degree, and finally human resources with graduate degrees.

This means that human resources with graduate degrees do not see a significant relationship between their job satisfaction and the level of organizational justice applied in the federation. Therefore, it can be said that the results were consistent with what the second hypothesis stated regarding the differences between human resources working in sports federations on the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction, which is due to educational qualification.

4. Verification of the differences between sample members by years of experience

To verify the validity of this variable, Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated to determine the size and type of the correlational relationship between the independent variable (organizational justice) and the dependent variable (job satisfaction) for human resources working in sports federations based on the following years of experience: (less than 5 years, 5-10 years, 10-15 years, and more than 15 years). The following was found:

Human resources working in sports federations with 5-10 years of experience are the most likely to experience a significant increase in job satisfaction as they perceive that there is a real application of organizational justice in the federation. This is followed by human resources with less than 5 years of experience, then human resources with 11-15 years of experience, and finally human resources with more than 15 years of experience. This means that human resources with more than 15 years of experience do not see a significant relationship between their job satisfaction and the level of organizational justice applied in the federation. Therefore, it can be said that the results were consistent with what the second hypothesis stated regarding the differences between human resources working in sports federations on the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction, which is due to years of experience.

5. Verification of the differences between sample members by job type

To verify the validity of this hypothesis, Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated to determine the size and type of the correlational relationship between the independent variable (organizational justice) and the dependent variable (job satisfaction) for both administrative and technical human resources working in sports federations. The following was found:

There are differences in the views of administrative and technical human resources on the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction. Administrative human resources believe that organizational justice has a strong correlation with job satisfaction, with a correlation coefficient of 0.743, which is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. Technical human resources believe that organizational justice has a moderate correlation with job satisfaction, with a correlation coefficient of 0.516, which is also statistically significant at the 0.01 level.

This means that administrative human resources working in sports federations see that their job satisfaction depends heavily on the level of organizational justice applied in the federation, more than technical human resources who see that their job satisfaction also depends on the level of organizational justice, but to a lesser extent than administrative human resources.

CONCLUSIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The job satisfaction of human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain is affected by the level of organizational justice applied in the federations in general, and distributive justice in particular.
2. Human resources working in sports federations in the Kingdom of Bahrain feel a high degree of satisfaction with supervision and follow-up, followed by satisfaction with promotions, and wages come in last place.
3. The opinions of human resources were characterized by a high degree of positivity about procedural justice, followed by interactional justice, and finally distributive justice.
4. The most important feature of distributive justice is the fair distribution of tasks and jobs to all human resources working in sports federations.
5. One of the most affected aspects of satisfaction by organizational justice in sports federations is promotions and career advancement.
6. The administrations of sports federations treat human resources with respect, objectivity, and equality.
7. Human resources working in sports federations feel the fairness of the incentives and rewards they receive whenever they provide outstanding performance, and sports federation's administrations allow any employee to appeal any decision related to promotions.
8. The feeling of satisfaction with organizational justice in sports federations increases as the age of human resources decreases, then decreases if the age of human resources is less than 25 years. That is, the highest age in terms of satisfaction with organizational justice is middle age, and satisfaction decreases at the extremes of age (younger-older).
9. Human resources with a bachelor's degree feel a high degree of satisfaction with organizational justice in sports federations more than other qualifications, and the feeling of satisfaction with organizational justice decreases among human resources as the number of years of experience increases.

RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

Based on the researcher's review of the results of the study and their analysis, especially the indicators that tend to be weak in one way or another, the following recommendations of the study can be formulated:

1. The incentive distribution system needs to be developed so that it is based directly and clearly on the efforts of human resources in the federation. Therefore, incentives must be linked to the performance of human resources.

2. There is an urgent need to find mechanisms that would increase the sense of fairness of promotions for human resources in sports federations compared to their colleagues in the federation or in other federations.
3. The administrations of sports federations should work to involve all human resources in decision-making that is approved by the administration, such as participating in the decision to organize local and international championships by developing work plans and preparation programs for hosting.
4. Work on developing procedures and mechanisms for tracking the violations of human resources in sports federations.
5. The supervision and follow-up style applied by the administrations of federations should be developed so that it reflects on the level of satisfaction of human resources, so that those who fall short are questioned and the performance of those who work hard is monitored.

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